

TRANSLATION STRATEGIES IN ALICE IN WONDERLAND'S RHYMES

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Abstract: *Poetry translation has always been regarded as the most difficult type of literary translation. When the object of translation is the multi-faceted, apparently nonsensical rhymes in Lewis Carroll's Alice in Wonderland, the translator's skill, competence and performance should be even greater. The present article aims at examining the strategies used in the published translations of Carroll's work in Romanian, evincing the similarity of effect on the target reader, which is normally presumed to be the ultimate objective of the literary translator. The analysis also attempts at evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of the translations under comparison according to the established assessment criteria in the field, in an attempt to discover if 'beauty' and 'truth' can ever be reconciled in the arduous task of literary translation.*

Key words: translation strategy, competence, performance, similarity of effect

Introduction

When considering poetry translation, the initial response is to deem it impossible or at least tremendously difficult. However, translators keep trying their hand at it, and the intertwining of literary talent and a sound command of the source and the target language sometimes yield great results.

The case of Lewis Carroll's whimsical poetry, loaded with jocular undertones, puns and allusions, poses multiple problems to any translator, however talented, as it requires a multifaceted approach, in tune with the writer's initial intentions; the main issue characterising a successful translation seems to be achieving similarity of effect on the target reader. The reader should not feel the target language variant as "forced" or "unnatural", which adds to the difficulty of the endeavour, as the source text is already loaded with numerous playful nuances that the translator or even the author may not have been aware of in the first place; thus, the translation should provide the same "feeling" as the original, and trigger a similar thought-provoking process in the recipient.

Translation of poetry

In point of defining translation and the translation process, the most suitable points of departure seem to be Nida's definition (1964), as it focuses on style and message when finding "the closest natural equivalent", and Toury's vision (1978), which stresses not only the linguistic, but also the unavoidable cultural dimension that are involved in "rewriting" an original text into a different language. In the same vein, Newmark (1991) sees translation as a "craft", replacing the initial

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written message in a certain language by the same message in another language, and thus requiring skills very similar to the process of creation of poetry itself.

Irrespective of the view one adopts, it goes without saying that the translation of poetry is a special case of translation, in need of the dynamic communicative approach focusing on similarity of effect mentioned above. Despite Roman Jakobson's opinion that it is by definition impossible, it is our view that both meanings and style may be rendered in the TT, with a considerable amount of effort, and inspiration. In keeping with Haroldo de Campos (2007), the main aim of poetry translation is not reconstituting the original referential message, but the "transcreation of several levels of semiotic processes". So, the translator should be as gifted as the initial author, and be on the same page with the latter in point of the auctorial intentions and the interpretation of the ST. Similarly, Ata and Queiroz (2016) see poetry translation as a multilevel problem-solving task, where the ST and the TT are the initial and final states of a continuous multifarious process.

Aim of analysis

The primary aim of the analysis refers to the evaluation and/or hierarchisation of the three published translation versions of the English corpus (the source text) into Romanian (the target texts), eventually proposing a fourth variant, our own, in which the author is trying to provide alternative solutions to the deficiencies noted in the other TTs. The passage from theory to practice is undoubtedly difficult and prone to numerous pitfalls, but the clearer insight into the various dimensions of the ST and their subsequent renderings into Romanian may serve as an advantageous point of departure for yet another translation, performed from a fresh perspective and issued from a solid theoretical background.

Methods of analysis

As in most cases of poetry translation evaluation, the method of choice was comparison and contrast, evincing the strong and weak points of each translated version of the poem in question. The comparison bore on all the levels of the literary text involved, i.e. semantic, syntactic, stylistic, and last but not least, prosodic (including the issues of phonology, rhyme, rhythm, and measure).

Despite its obvious limitations, this method is the only one possible in tackling the arduous task of assessing poetry translations, as the subjective dimension plays a major role in such an endeavour. The interplay of the cognitive and the interpretative facets makes it hard to be entirely fair in the evaluative work, and the entire matter eventually boils down to the taste of the evaluator. However, the present paper is an attempt at going beyond the empirical scope which this method inevitably entails, in an attempt to punctually analyse all the aspects that go into the making of poetry, both in content and form.

Data analysis and findings

The very first issue that arrests the reader's attention is the form of the source text (ST), a rather naïve children's rhyme with a very simple two-stanza structure and a lively rhythm. Obviously not a piece of great literary value, the poem is to be found in the second chapter of *Alice in Wonderland*, and is meant to be recited by Alice herself, who cannot precisely remember it and thus ends up with a rather odd, although funny version.

When performing the preliminary analysis, the translator should first and foremost be aware of the cultural background of the ST, which is a parody of the well-known educational children's rhyme *Against Idleness and Mischief* by Isaac Watts, whose first line reads "How doth the little busy bee". The intentional replacement of the bee, seen as the personification of hard work and diligence, with the personified crocodile, the epitome of cruelty and deceit, is obviously meant as a criticism of the Victorian mores in general, and the rather ineffective teaching methods of the time in particular.

Isaac Watts's rhyme	Alice's version (ST)
How doth the little busy Bee Improve each shining Hour, And gather Honey all the day From every opening Flower!	How doth the little crocodile Improve his shining tail, And pour the waters of the Nile On every golden scale!
How skilfully she builds her Cell! How neat she spreads the Wax! And labours hard to store it well With the sweet Food she makes.	How cheerfully he seems to grin, How neatly spreads his claws, And welcomes little fishes in, With gently smiling jaws!

It is easily noticeable that besides the rhythm and measure, the syntactic skeleton (even preserving certain words and phrases like *how doth the little* in line 1, *improve* and *shining* in line 2, *every* in line 4, *how neat* [...] *spreads* in line 6) is identical, making it impossible for the initiated audience to miss such an overt intertextual reference. The jocular and parodic intentions are easy to discern in the author's substituting the sedulous work of the bee (a familiar creature in Europe) meant to teach young children the highly-praised Victorian values of diligence, perseverance and generosity, by the deceitful and downright predatory actions of the exotic crocodile. Obviously, such an intertextual allusion cannot possibly be paralleled in translation, but what the Romanian translator can do is to preserve the light-hearted tone and lively rhythm specific to children's rhymes.

Here are the three Romanian version of the poem identified in different editions of the book, published by various publishing houses in the past decades:

TT1 – translation by Ioana Ieronim 2016	TT2 – translation by Vasile Poenaru 1999	TT3 – translation by Mihaela Istrati 2010
Cum face micul crocodil Să-și țină luciul pe coadă? El toarnă apele din Nil Pe fiecare solz, la scaldă!	Ce lucitoare coadă-și face Micuțul crocodil Și-și scaldă orice solz de aur În apele din Nil!	Cum face micul crocodil Ca mai bună lucioasa-i coadă să devie, Și toarnă apele din Nil Pe fiece solz de culoare aurie?
Voios rânjește apoi din falcă Și ghearele-și întinde, Așa invită peștișori Și-n zâmbet îi cuprinde.	Ce vesel pare să rânjească Cum gheare-ntinde lin, Poftind micuții pești în gura-i Cu fălci zâmbind senin!	Ce plin de voioșie pare că rânjește, Și ce dibaci ghearele-i se desfășor, Iar peștișorii înăuntru îi poftește, Cu fălcile-i surâzând încetișor!

From a prosodic point of view, the measure is generally preserved (7-8 syllables), with the notable exception in most lines of TT3, which proves detrimental to the overall musicality of the poem, disrupting the playful and cheerful rhythm. In point of sonority, TT2 seems to reach its goal, while TT3 ranks last in this respect, as it seemed to pay more attention to the rhyming pattern and thus lengthened the lines inappropriately.

As far as rhyme is concerned, the initial ABAB crossed pattern was only observed in TT3, the other translations opting for the easier solution of rhyming only the even lines. In this respect, it is our personal opinion that the rhyming pattern may be reduced to a minimum, by taking into account the TL constraints, as long as the measure and rhythm are closer to the original. The impact of the cheerful tone is undoubtedly greater than the strict observance of the rhyming pattern, although the latter is also desirable if possible.

In point of phonology, it is worth mentioning that all the TTs manage to preserve, within limits, the alliteration in the liquid consonant *l*, suggesting the water flow, and maybe the great cycle of life, which sees the rather gruesome image of the crocodile eating fish as normal, even playful.

Regarding the syntactic aspect, it may be said that all TTs are generally accurate, preserving both juxtaposition and the syntactic categories of most of the key words. However, it was to be expected, since the structure is fairly simple and without any syntactic ramifications that would pose translation problems. The repetitive pattern starting with "how" is present in all TTs, although it is visible that TT2 reverses the order of the lines in the first stanza, probably to the purpose of increasing the clarity and naturalness of expression.

Semantically speaking, it is evident that TT2 is the least affected by semantic loss, a shortcoming that can be found in all the other versions, especially at the level of descriptive epithets and adverbs of manner.

In order to have a clearer view of the notional words and phrases in the TTs, the following table might be useful:

ST	TT1	TT2	TT3
improve his shining tail	să-și țină luciul pe coadă	a-și face lucitoare coadă	mai bună lucioasa-i coadă să devie
to pour	a turna	a scălda	a turna
golden scale	solz	solz de aur	solz de culoare aurie
to grin cheerfully	a rânji voios	a rânji vesel	a rânji plin de voieșie
to spread claws	a întinde gheare	a întinde gheare	a se desfășura gheare
neatly	-	lin	dibaci
to welcome in	a invita	a pofti	a pofti
gently	-	senin	încetșor
smiling jaws	zâmbet din falcă	fălci zâmbind	fălci surâzând

It is easily noticeable that displacement affects mostly TT1—the second stanza, and TT2—the first stanza. While in the latter case the choice is quite questionable, as it affects the very beginning of the poem and leads to a quite forced and unnatural word-order, the former case completely disrupts the syntax by anteposing *falcă* and occasioning stylistically-marked constructions like “a rânji din falcă” and “a cuprinde în zâmbet”. These instances qualify TT1 as “the most poetical” of all three, as it uses a sort of linguistic combinations that are not normally used in everyday conversation, and thus may be deemed as rather unsuitable for a children’s poem. The same stylistic markedness catches the reader’s eye in TT3, which uses the outdated verbal form “să devie” and the oddly conjugated phrase “ghearele-i se desfășor”, resulting in a quite strained version that children are very unlikely to find appealing. After all, nursery rhymes are intended to be easy to memorise, and all these odd, “literary” turns of phrase and the overall verbosity affecting TT3 do not aid in this respect. In point of metric, TT2 seems to be the most end-user-friendly, although it has various deficiencies, as shown above.

Upon examining the translation strategies used, the most common seem to be displacement and compensation, while TT3 mostly relies on literal translation, which also makes it the least successful. The former is most visible in TT2, in the first stanza which reverses the order of all the lines, probably in order to preserve the only rhyming pair, i.e. *crocodil-Nil*. The latter is more saliently used in TT1, where the determiner *shining* in the phrase *shining tail* becomes an anteposed noun –*luciul pe coadă*. TT1 is also the most affected by semantic loss, as it fails to translate the verb *to seem* in line 5, the adjective *golden* in line 4, the adverbs *neatly* in line 6

and *gently* in line 8, as well as by semantic gain, as apparent in the addition of *la scaldă* (line 4) and the verb *a cuprinde* (line 8), also for rhyming reasons.

Taking all these into account, it is probably not devoid of interest to propose a fourth TT that may reconcile form and meaning, solving and/or avoiding some of the shortcomings seen in the other versions analysed above (like omissions, displacements, semantic losses and/or gains, strange or forced wordings, disruptions of rhythm, inaccuracies of measure, etc):

Cum face micul crocodil
Să-și țină luciul cozii,
Să-și toarne apele din Nil
Sa-și aurească solzii !

Cum râde plin de voieșie
Cu rășchirate gheare,
Ca peștișorii toți să vie
În fălci surâzătoare!
(our own version)

Inspired by the previously analysed TTs, this version "borrows" the formulation *plin de voieșie* in line 5 from TT3, as well as change of the grammatical category of the noun phrase *shining tail* in line 2 into the genitival combination *luciul cozii* as shown in the nominal transformation in TT2. Similarly, just like in TT3 line 7 employs a rather obsolete form of the verb, *să vie*, as required by the rhyming pattern; however, the effect is no longer exaggerated and it may be considered as hinting to the Victorian century when the ST was written. Likewise, there are some notable omissions, like the verb *to seem* in line 5, the adverbs *neatly* in line 6 and *gently* in line 8, as well as instances of literal translation, as in line 8, where *smiling jaws* is rendered as *fălci surâzătoare*.

As far as the elements of novelty brought by this version, the following are worth mentioning: the semantic gain *râde* as the equivalent of *to grin* in line 5 (due to metric constraints), and the compensation used in line 4 (where the determiner *golden* becomes the verb *a auri*), and in line 6 (where the verb phrase *spreads his claws* is rendered as the noun phrase *rășchirate gheare*). Moreover, this TT is the only one displaying a full ABAB rhyming pattern that is not unnatural, a bouncy rhythm and a similar measure to the original, being closer to the similarity of effect that a literary translation is supposed to produce.

Conclusions

All in all, despite the relative brevity of expression and simplicity of message, the two stanzas of the ST gave rise to extremely varied TTs, each having its strengths and weaknesses. All TTs manage to convey the meaning quite accurately by means of translation strategies like compensation and displacement, being more or

less affected by semantic loss and/or gain. In a subjective attempt at hierarchizing them, it may well be said that TT2 seems to be the most successful version, closer to the original's rhythm and measure, and most likely to appeal to its intended audience—children, followed by TT1, deemed as the most “poetic” of all three, also easy to recite and memorise, but negatively affected by odd turns and phrases, as in the final line, and numerous omissions; finally, the least successful of the TTs is TT3, which comes out as awkward and verbose, as it mainly resorts to literal translation, and disregards prosodic and musical aspects, in quite an unsuitable manner for poetry translation. It is our opinion that the version proposed in the present paper, although by no means perfect, manages to solve some of the deficiencies found in the TTs analysed.

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